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Exploration of environmental contaminants in honeybees using GC-TOF-MS and GC-Orbitrap-MS

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT

This study reports an analytical approach by gas chromatography and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) intended to be used for investigation of non-targeted environmental contaminants in honeybees. The approach involves a generic extraction and analysis with two GC-HRMS systems: time-of-flight and Orbitrap analyzers, GC-TOF-MS, and GC-Orbitrap-MS operated in electron-impact ionization (EI) mode. The workflow for screening of non-targeted contaminants consisted of initial peak detection by deconvolution and matching the first-stage mass spectra EI-MS with a nominal mass spectral library. To gain further confidence in the structural characterization of the contaminants under investigation, molecular formula of representative ions (molecular and fragment ions) was provided for those with an accurate mass scoring (error ≤ 5 ppm). This methodology was applied for screening environmental contaminants in 75 samples of adult honeybee. This approach has provided the tentative identification of environmental contaminants belonging to different chemical groups, among them, PAHs, phthalates and synthetic musks. Residues of veterinary treatments used in apiculture were also detected in the honeybee samples.

Keywords: Honeybee; Environmental contaminants; GC-EI-TOF-MS; GC-Orbitrap-MS; Non-targeted screening

1. Introduction

Uptake of environmental contaminants by organisms occurs by a variety of routes of exposure, and most commonly through inhalation, ingestion, or dermal sorption. Contaminants enter the environment both directly from natural and anthropogenic processes and indirectly from a non-intentionally production during waste incineration, combustion of fossil fuels, or the deterioration of discarded synthetic materials (Bogdal et al., 2013). Several species of insects have been documented to be exposed to contaminants, and have been used as bioindicators to monitor environmental pollution apart from evaluating species diversity and abundance (Kevan, 1999). This is because insects have strong relationship with ecology and are taken as being sensitive to habitat disturbance of the conditions of terrestrial or aquatic ecosystems.

Pollinators are bioindicators as individuals and populations; most research has been focused in honeybees since they can be managed in easily transportable boxes for pollination of crops and for getting bee- hive products (Celli and Maccagnani, 2003). Bees are excellent biological indicators of the level of contamination in their living environments because they are capable of capturing and accumulating contaminants, reside in diverse habitats and cover large areas of several square kilometers from the hive (Bargańska et al., 2016). The transfer to the own body of honeybee may vary according to the environmental scenario or foraging area, climatological conditions, physico-chemical properties of chemicals and, according to the exposure routes and the biology of the bee. Unfortunately, our understanding of how to evaluate whether environmental contamination affect honeybees is poor; few papers report experimentations running in field conditions and most of them are focused only in pesticides (Benuszak et al., 2017). Exposure can be exemplified by the investigation of pollen, beeswax or honey which may become contaminated with various industrial pollutants (Chiesa et al., 2016, 2018; de Oliveira et al., 2016; Dżugan et al., 2018; Gómez-Ramos et al., 2016). Stand out above all the studies about the detection of metals (Dżugan et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2018); and to a much lesser extent, the investigation of organic contaminants in the body of honey- bee, such as the target analysis of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (Amorena et al., 2009; Kargar et al., 2017; Lambert et al., 2012; Perugini et al., 2009) or polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) (Anderson and Wojtas, 1986; Morse et al., 1987). Most analytical methods reported in literature for the evaluation of organic pollutants are focused on a limited list of target compounds. Gas chromatography (GC) coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) is commonly used for the

determination of non-polar and volatile contaminants, contributing to remarkable advantages in sensitivity and selectivity, but this approach do not provide a wide scope screening to explore a large number of chemicals (Elbashir and Aboul-Enein, 2018; Hernández et al., 2015; Serrano et al., 2011).

Determination of environmental contaminants needs the development of screening strategies. What implies stringent demands in the level of reliability for identify contaminants, which in turn depends on the large and continually increasing number of chemicals, some of which are known unequivocally as hazardous. Although single analyzers, such as quadrupole (GC-MS) can be used for the detection of contaminants using nominal spectral libraries, high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) is a superior technique for a screening purpose. In a wide range of analytical contexts, HRMS has been identified as the method of choice because of its ability to measure accurate masses and more importantly, structural information. This makes it suitable for applications focused in the identification of unknown structures or in the detection of non-targeted contaminants. In the last few years, atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) has been implemented in GC-HRMS instruments offering attractive features for the screening. However electron ionization (EI) is the most widely applied technique due to its robustness, reproducibility and the existence of standardized commercial libraries, which facilitates the identification of compounds (Hernández et al., 2015). Multiclass screening methods using GC-EI- TOF-MS has been successfully applied for the investigation of organic pollutants in environmental samples using different search strategies based on nominal spectral libraries (Pitarch et al., 2016) or accurate mass spectral libraries (Hakme et al., 2017). On the other hand, GC-EI- Q-Orbitrap-MS is a new technology that became commercially available for the first time in 2015 (Mol et al., 2016). It has the advantage of working with a high resolving power (up to 120 K at m/z 200) and mass accuracy lower than 1 ppm, but its potential for the detection of non-targeted contaminants in the environment, and particularly in bees has not been sufficiently explored.

The aim of this study was to investigate whether an analytical approach based on gas chromatography and high-resolution mass spectrometry with two GC-HRMS systems: time-of-flight and Orbitrap analyzers (GC-TOF-MS, and GC-Orbitrap-MS), provides useful capabilities for screening of non-preselected environmental contaminants and further tentative identification. This analytical strategy is basically intended to be used for characterizing the presence of GC amenable environmental contaminants, when this issue has not been sufficiently addressed in the honeybee.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample preparation and processing

Samples of adult bees were collected from different apiaries, for exploring the presence of environmental contaminants. Apiaries from different regions of Spain (Table S1) were selected depending of diverse landscapes, such as agricultural areas with conventional practices of pesticide applications or proximity to urban areas. Samples of adult bees were collected by qualified veterinarians. Approx. 10 g of sample were collected from the bottom of the beehive, presumably with a higher proportion of foragers. The honeybee colonies were housed in Langstroth hives and managed according to a conventional production. A well-established and generic method was selected as extraction procedure for the analysis of various analyte classes; the QuEChERS method is a sample preparation technique with an ever-widening applications base including the non-selective ones for screening analysis. In this work, bee samples were treated using the QuEChERS methodology modified, applying an ultrasonic probe (Gil García et al., 2018). QuEChERS approach is in accordance with so-called green chemistry due to low solvent consumption, energy consumption, absence of chlorinated solvents and a reduced waste generation (Stocka et al., 2011). This procedure is described in brief; 2 g of bee samples were weighed into a 50 mL centrifuge tube PTFE to which 2 mL of ultrapure water was added. The tube was shaken manually and laid down for 5 min. Later, 5 mL of acetonitrile was added on top of 20 μL of a 10 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of surrogate standard solution of triphenylphosphate (TPP). The mix was homogenized using a sonicator at an amplitude of 75% for 2 min 20 s (alternatively, sonication for 12 s and a stand for 2 s). 2 g of anhydrous magnesium sulfate, 0.5 g of sodium chloride, 0.5 g trisodium citrate and 0.25 g disodium hydrogencitrate sesquihydrate were added. The samples were shaken in an automatic axial extractor (AGYTAX®; Cirta Lab S.L., Madrid, Spain) for 5 min and then were centrifuged for 5 min at 3500 ppm. 3 mL of the supernatant were transferred to a tube containing 125 mg of PSA, 125 mg of Z-Sep and 750 mg of MgSO_4 . It was vortexed for 1 min and then centrifuged for 5 min at 3500 rpm. 10 μL of 5% formic acid in acetonitrile was added to the final extract in order to stabilize the compounds prone to degradation at high pH. Prior to honeybee sample injection, reagent blanks were analyzed to identify any possible systematic or non-systematic contamination from the equipment or used materials. For injection on GC-EI-TOF-MS, 125 μL of the extract were evaporated by a gentle nitrogen flow and were reconstituted with 50 μL of cyclohexane to have a final

extract of 1 g sample/mL. For the injection on GC-QOrbitrap-MS 125 μL of the extract were evaporated and reconstituted with 125 μL of ethyl acetate to have a final extract of 0.4 g sample mL^{-1} .

2.2. Analysis by GC-EI-TOF-MS

The separation of the organic compounds from the extracts was carried out using an Agilent 7890A gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA). The samples were injected using a multimode injector inlet in splitless mode with an ultra-inert inlet liner, with a glass wool frit obtained from Agilent. The injection volume was 2 μL and was carried out at 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Helium (99.999% purity) was used as the carrier gas. The GC separation was performed using two fused silica HP-5MS UI capillary column of 15 m \times 0.25 mm inner diameter and a film thickness of 0.25 μm (from Agilent) connected by a capillary flow technology (CFT) union. The oven temperature was programmed as follows: 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 min; 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and finally up to 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. The total run time was 40.5 min with two additional minutes for backflushing at 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Backflushing was used to shorten the analysis time and reduce system maintenance avoiding the arrival of undesirable compounds of the matrix to the detector. The end of the chromatographic column is connected to the second column through a CFT union (used as purged capillary flow device), which allows system backflushing. During the run time, the flow was set at 1.0 mL min^{-1} in the first column and 1.2 mL min^{-1} in the second column (with a difference of 0.2 mL min^{-1} over the flow in the first column). Once the analysis is finished, there is a 2 min post-run time where a change in the flow is set: 6 mL min^{-1} in the second column and consequently the flow in the first column decreased to 5.7 mL min^{-1} .

The source and interface temperatures were set to 150 and 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively, and a solvent delay of 4 min was selected in order to prevent damage in the ion source filament. Retention time locked (RTL) setting was used to eliminate the need for adjusting retention times of the compounds, for further analysis when needed. Chlorpyrifos methyl was used as locking compound at the retention time of 18.11 min. The instrument worked at constant flow.

The gas chromatography system was connected to a quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) mass spectrometer Agilent 7200 (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA), operating in electron-impact ionization (EI) mode (70 eV). The ion source and quadrupole analyzer temperatures were set at 280 and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. TOF-MS was operated at 4 GHz (12,000 FWHM), with acquisition over the mass range of m/z

45–550. Perfluorotributylamine (PFTBA) was used for daily MS calibration. The mass accuracy of the generated ions was controlled using an internal mass calibration performed before each injection. This calibration can be programmed in the worklist, and when the internal mass calibration performed between the samples showed mass errors higher than 5 ppm, the sequence was automatically stopped to ensure the accuracy of the masses.

2.3. Analysis by GC-Orbitrap-MS

A GC-Q-Orbitrap system (Q Exactive GC, Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany) consisting of a TriPlus RSH autosampler, a TRACE 1310 GC with a hot split/splitless injector, an electron ionization (EI) source, a hybrid quadrupole Orbitrap mass spectrometer with an HCD cell was used. The injector was equipped with a single taper liner (78.5 mm × 4 mm ID × 6.5 mm ED). Hot splitless injection was performed (1 µL, 250 °C, splitless time 1 min). The injection volume was 1 µL and was carried out at 250 °C. Helium (99.999% purity) was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow of 1.2 mL min⁻¹. GC separation was performed on a 30 m × 0.25 mm ID, 0.25 µm TG-5SilMS column with 5 m safeward (Thermo Scientific) using the following temperature program: 40 °C (1.5 min), 25 °C/min to 90 °C (1.5 min), 25 °C/min to 180 °C (0 min), 5 °C/min to 300 °C (0 min), 10 °C/min to 300 °C (5 min).

EI was performed at 70 eV with the source temperature set at 250 °C. Full scan MS acquisition was done in profile mode using a *m/z* range of 50–550. Nitrogen gas was used for the *C-trap* and HCD cell (99.999% purity). The *maximum ion injection time* was set to 'AUTO'. This corresponded to 135 ms for resolving power settings of 60 K and the AGC target at 1×10^6 (balance scan). The actual scan speed under these conditions was approximately 7.4 scans/s. The instrument was controlled using Tune version 2.7 and Xcalibur 4.0 software (Thermo Scientific). Mass calibration was performed before each sequence using perfluorotributylamine. During the analysis, internal mass calibration was performed by the instrument using three background ions from the column bleed as lock mass (C₅H₁₅O₃Si₃, 207.0323; C₇H₂₁O₄Si₄, 281.0511; C₉H₂₇O₅Si₅, 355.0699) with a search window of ±2 ppm. If in a certain scan, when none of the 3 background ions were found within ±2 ppm of their exact mass, no internal locking was done for that scan.

For data processing Xcalibur 4.1 and TraceFinder 4.0 software (Thermo Scientific) were used. This tool allowed peak detection with spectral deconvolution and tentative compound identification against the library NIST for the candidate compounds. To

study and process EI-Orbitrap spectra, the NIST Mass Spectral Library & Search Software (NIST 2014/EPA/NIH) was used, containing over 276.000 spectra.

2.4. Data analysis and workflow for screening of non-targeted contaminants

Two HRMS systems, GC-EI-TOF-MS and GC-EI-Orbitrap-MS, working at two resolving powers (120KWHM and 60K FWHM respectively) were used for the detection of non-targeted contaminants in honey- bees. GC-Orbitrap-MS is a new technology that has the advantage of working with a high resolving power (up to 120 K at m/z 200) and mass accuracy lower than 1 ppm. In both HRMS search methodologies, compound identification was performed by comparing electron ionization MS spectrum of unknowns with the NIST Library. However, the identification process is different since it is based on search algorithms which are implemented in each GC-HRMS instrument as well as the certainty of identification, that is defined by the spectral match and fit factor established in each instrument.

The workflow for a non-targeted screening, initially consisted of peak detection. Using the Unknowns Analysis tool in Agilent MassHunter Quantitative Analysis Software B.07.00 (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA), data were processed by the procedure often named “chromatographic peak deconvolution”. Chromatographic peak deconvolution was performed with a parameter named “retention time window size factor” with a value of 50 and 100. This is a dimensionless parameter, equivalent to the correlation time window multiplied by the expected peak sharpness (DeltaCounts/min). An accurate mass extraction window of ± 0.5 Da and a sharpness threshold of 25% were set. The last parameter is related to the peak shape and represents the maximum decline rate of the integrated peak. Only compounds with 3 or more ions (up to 10) were registered. As result, this parameter controls the grouping of extracted ion chromatograms (XIC peaks) into components. For GC-Orbitrap-MS, each datafile was deconvoluted to extract individual peaks from the total ion chromatogram (TIC) using “Deconvolution Plugging” application within TraceFinder 4.0 software (Thermo Scientific). Peak deconvolution was processed using “all ions” option for the use of all ions in the deconvoluted spectra for library search, an accurate mass extraction window of 5 ppm, a s/n threshold of 3, a minimum TIC intensity signal of 1×10^5 and an ion overlap window of 98%. This parameter controls the grouping of XIC peaks around each compound's base peak. The higher the ion overlap window percentage, the less likely ions generated from two compounds are grouped within the same spectrum.

In the second step of the workflow, tentative identification was done by comparison

of the cleaned spectrum for each peak obtained from peak deconvolution with the NIST nominal mass spectral library (version 11), which contains EI spectra of N200.000 compounds. Comparison of GC-TOF-MS data with the spectral library was carried out setting a minimum match factor score of 70 and a ratio percent uncertainty of 40. By GC-QOrbitrap-MS, the list of tentative hits returned for each peak are scored based on a combination of a classical search index (SI) score and high-resolution filtering (HRF) value. The HRF value is the percentage of the spectrum that can be explained by the chemical formula proposed from the best library match result. Minimum setting score for GC-Orbitrap-MS were established at 80.

The final stage was to use the accurate mass data of fragment ions in order to support the proposed formula and to derive structural elucidation. For GC-TOF-MS data, Molecular Formula Generator and the Mass Formula Calculator tools within MassHunter Qualitative Analysis software, were used for identification of the compounds. The software NIST tool, MS Interpreter was used for a correct structure assignment of the fragments ions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural elucidation of environmental contaminants

Both techniques proved to be a powerful tool for the tentative identification of non-targeted contaminants in adult-honeybees sampled from apiaries located in rural and urban areas. Among them are PAHs, phthalates, and synthetic musks. The screening workflow for the characterization of non-targeted compounds with both GC-MS systems followed three key steps. [Figs. 1 and 2](#) display the workflow followed by GC-TOF-MS and GC-Orbitrap-MS. As example, it is shown the structural elucidation of HHCB (1,3,4,6,7,8-hexahydro-4,6,6,7,8,8-hexamethyl-cyclopenta-[g]-2-benzopyrane (Galaxolide(TM))). The initial detection of compounds started with the chromatographic deconvolution as automatic analysis of the background noise level; it is a search process of those ions with higher signal intensity and grouping of those spectrum ions with the same Rt, for which it is assumed that they come from the same compound. [Fig. 1a](#) presents the chromatographic deconvolution into the detection of 1326 peaks with ± 0.5 Da accurate mass extraction window and with a "retention time window size factor" of 50 and 100 by GC-TOF-MS. Of 1326 peaks, 192 peaks display a matching score ≥ 70 with the nominal mass spectrum library, significantly limiting the data to be analyzed (aprox. 14% of data). [Fig. 1a](#) displays an overlapping of several XIC grouped

at Rt 17.36 min, corresponding to 5 representative ions at m/z 171, 213, 243, 244 and 258 belonging to the same compound. Ionization through EI, generally generates fragment-rich mass spectra at a standard ionization energy of 70 eV. The deconvoluted mass spectrum is searched in the NIST library to elucidate the chemical structure. The library search for the first-stage mass spectra can be performed using low- and high resolution MS, by GC-TOF-MS and GC-Orbitrap-MS, respectively. By GC-TOF-MS, the full approach for the characterization of non-targeted compounds comprised a preliminary identification which was based on a good match with the NIST library, working with data obtained in low resolution and a posterior processing of data of accurate mass measurements for the generation of the elemental composition using high-resolution and mass spectral interpretation. A score of 85.3 provides an indication of how well the deconvoluted mass spectrum matches the nominal mass spectrum library. Fig. 1b shows a XIC corresponding to the calculated exact mass for the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{26}O$ with a mass tolerance of ± 20 ppm. The accurate mass spectrum of the molecular ion at m/z 258.1972 correlates well to the calculated exact mass for the elemental composition $[C_{18}H_{26}O]^+$ with a mass error of -0.93 ppm. Other structural features provide confidence in the structural elucidation. The high fit between the theoretical isotopic abundance C^{13}/C^{12} ratio and spacing with the sample spectrum is observed (red rectangles at the mass spectrum), reflected by a score of 94.19. At least 6 rings and double bonds (DBE, double bond equivalents, calculated from valence values of elements) are consistent with this molecular formula. The accurate mass measurements of fragment ions at m/z 243.1743, 213.1638, 187.1117 and 171.1169 with mass errors of -0.63 , 0.02 , 2.12 and -1.37 ppm (Table 1), were sufficient to determine the elemental compositions ($C_{17}H_{23}O$, $C_{16}H_{21}$, $C_{13}H_{15}O$, $C_{13}H_{15}$) respectively, and to confidently identify this non-targeted compound as HHCB.

The GC-Orbitrap-MS also combines the features of mass fragmentation and accurate mass measurement of fragment ions as additional tool for structural elucidation of non-targeted compounds. Fig. 2 shows an example of compound detection and identification. Out of all the plausible compounds, a total of 168 peaks displayed a SI threshold of 700 and a total score of 80, eliminating approx. 93% of data to be analyzed. The deconvoluted spectrum was first searched against NIST library. HRF and SI values of 98.6 and 833 provided a confidence in an initial tentative identification. The combination of accurate mass matching and structural elucidation with the ions observed in the mode named "all ions" provide reliability to the identification of this non-targeted compound. The specific ions observed in the mass spectrum correlated well with the characteristic fragmentation patterns of HHCB; with the consecutive loss of two methyl

groups from the molecular ion leading to the signals at m/z 243.1743 and 213.1638. A loss of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}$ which, results in a distinctive ion observed at m/z 171.1169. A series of fragment ions, similar to that obtained by GC-TOF-MS analysis, was observed. The fragment ions at m/z 243.1743, 213.1638, 187.1117 and 171.1169 matched to the same elemental compositions, before indicated, with sub-1-ppm mass error (0.98, 0.33, 0.07 and 0.15 ppm respectively, [Table 2](#)).

HHCB is a high production volume (HPV) chemical (in the range of 5000 to 10,000 tons) according to the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Chemical Substances ([EINEC, 2008](#)). Its potential release into the environment can take place during the production phase (compounding and formulation) but it is mostly discharged with water into the sewer system after consumer use. It is widely used as scent component in an extensive range of domestic or industrial products such as cleaning or washing agents, and disinfectants. Several monitoring studies have evidenced the presence of HHCB in aquatic environments ([Gómez et al., 2012](#); [Mogensen et al., 2004](#)), in sewage treatment plant (STP) effluents and in surface waters ([Gómez et al., 2012](#); [Gómez et al., 2011](#)). Honeybees need water for several functions. Depending on climatic conditions, they use water to thermoregulate the hive by evaporative cooling on warmest months and to keep the brood nest area at the proper relative humidity. Some honeybees in the colony are specialized on water collection and they find water in a number of places including drops adhered to vegetation and water sources such as puddles, ponds, agricultural and urban runoff, etc. Such water sources may also contain pesticides or other chemicals, what could be related to the presence of this contaminant in adult bees. HHCB was detected up to 56% of the samples, including samples from areas with rural and urban influence.

The findings about the exposure of plastic additives such as phthalates, or esters of phthalic acid (PAEs), evidence their widespread in the environment ([Gao and Wen, 2016](#)). As phthalates are not chemically bound to the plastic products, they are easily released into the environment. Although some phthalates exhibit various abiotic and biotic degradation pathways, they can be found in the environment due to the high production volumes and an almost continuous release into the environment because leaching, migration, or evaporation during use ([European Chemicals Agency, 2013](#)). They have been found in soil, sediments, drinking water, atmospheric air, indoor air, wastewater, dust and aquatic biota. These chemicals are ubiquitous in the environment, but very few studies have reported the detection or impact of phthalates on wild terrestrial species or on insects ([Przybylińska and Wyszowski, 2016](#)). It is worth mentioning in this line, that phthalates may be trapped on ant cuticles which are mostly

coated with long-chain hydrocarbons (Lenoir et al., 2012, 2016). The function of the epicuticle or lipid layer as principal barrier to the movement of water through the cuticle have been extensively studied (Blomquist and Bagneres, 2010; Noble- Nesbitt, 1970). However, little is known about structure of the cuticle, its variations within and between insects, when considering penetration of substances through it. On the other hand, the lipid layer of the epicuticle may offer little resistance to the penetration of apolar sub- stances. The rate at which a compound moves depends on variables such as the thickness of the cuticle, or the presence or absence of pore canals. The partition coefficient of a contaminant is especially significant as well as the presence of lipid micelles in wax canals which may provide a pathway for the penetration of lipophilic substances from the ambient (Noble-Nesbitt, 1970). This could explain an adsorption process in the fat body and the detection of phthalates in samples of honeybees. Diethyl phthalate (DEP) and Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) were detected up to 8% of the samples. The hits obtained by library search of mass spectra provided hints of presence of phthalates in bee samples. The distinctive mass spectrum of phthalates is given by the presence and intensity of characteristic fragment ions corresponding to a non-random distribution of molecular sub-structures. Under EI conditions, it is not possible occasionally to detect the molecular ion, but the similitude between mass spectra makes attainable elucidation of structurally related compounds. The presence of the characteristic ion observed in the EI spectra of phthalates at m/z 149 commonly used to identify phthalates, aid correlation with fragmentation pattern of phthalates (Fig. 3). The two major pathways by McLafferty rearrangement or by the loss of alkoxy group involves a carbonyl oxygen attack to the ortho-carbonyl carbon (Jeilani et al., 2011) leading to structures with tetrahedral carbon intermediates that eventually give m/z 149. The measured m/z at 149 was within a mass deviation of 0.7 and -4.8 ppm for DEP and DEHP respectively, compared to the calculated exact mass and consistent with the empirical formula of $C_8H_5O_3$. The accurate mass data available for other fragment ions observed in EI spectra helped in the assignation of structures using GC- TOF-MS. The molecular formula generated for each fragment ion, consistent with structural features of phthalates, is included in Table 1. The measured m/z of fragment ions correlated well to the following elemental compositions within a mass deviation below ± 4.8 ppm compared to the calculated exact mass: DEP (m/z 176.0468, $C_{10}H_8O_3$; m/z 177.0546, $C_{10}H_9O_3$, m/z 105.0335, C_7H_5O) and DEHP (m/z 279.1509, $C_{16}H_{23}O_4$; m/z 167.0339, $C_8H_7O_4$). Table 2 also shows the identification of phthalates by GC-Orbitrap-MS using a confidence score that takes into account the NIST spectral match as well as the percentage of fragment ions that can be explained from the elemental composition of

the molecular ion assigned by NIST. The identification was based on an average total score N 90 in the samples, the library spectral match, the deconvoluted spectrum, as well as a list of the measured fragments ions with ppm mass deviations below ± 0.88 . The phthalates DEP, phthalic acid, cyclobutyl isobutyl ester and 1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid, butyl cyclohexyl ester were identified up to 16% of the samples. The detection of phthalates may be explained by the migration from plastic components of some hive frames which function is to hold the suspended bee wax comb in the hive (Gómez-Ramos et al., 2016). Apart from the exposure via, either atmospheric air, or air inside the hive, other possible via is the collection of water. Although some phthalates tend to bind to sediments and suspended particles, a small amount is dissolved in the water column and constitutes another vehicle for the dispersion in aquatic ecosystems (European Chemicals Agency, 2013; Gao and Wen, 2016).

In bee wax comb samples, other environmental contaminants such as PAHs have been detected (Gómez-Ramos et al., 2016). Beeswax is a lipidic matrix where many environmental contaminants, chemicals with lipophilic nature can be retained. PAHs may be found both in the gas and the particulate phase of ambient air; they range from semivolatile molecules to molecules with high boiling points. PAHs mostly come from the incomplete combustion of organic (carbonaceous) materials or pyrolysis, either naturally or anthropogenically derived, transported from remote sites, deposited in soil and re-evaporated to the atmosphere, depending on meteorological conditions, and atmospheric physics. They are ubiquitous in the environment because they are commonly detected in air, soil, and water. And, owing to the fact that several PAHs are toxic and carcinogens, some of them are monitored as a priority by the competent administrations in pollution control. The broad distribution of PAHs in the environment and in biota has been well documented (Bartrons et al., 2016). Smaller airborne particulates containing PAHs may be easily inhaled for birds or insects. Studies on honeybees have shown to be useful as indicators of environmental quality, since during foraging flights they cover a large sample area. Monitoring of exposure to various environmental contaminants has already been carried out; including heavy metals (Zhou et al., 2018) and PAHs, detected in the body of bees or in beehive products (Lambert et al., 2012; Perugini et al., 2009). PAHs have been detected in higher frequency, up to approx. 50% of the samples, also including samples with agricultural and urban influence. Next to deconvolution, the best match with score better than 77 was for diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP) by GC-TOF-MS analysis. DIPN mixture of up to ten isomers is used industry, among other, as solvent in manufacturing of printing materials;

it is a hydrophobic modifier of plastic materials. The library search on the GC-MS data identified for some DIPN isomers. Up to four of the ten possible isomers appeared in the chromatograms. The EI mass spectra, assigned as DINP by library search, shows the same characteristic base peak at m/z 197; other MS peaks were at m/z 169 and 155 corresponding with loss of methyl groups from the molecular ion at m/z 212. With the GC-TOF-MS system, the mass accuracy of the molecular and fragment ions correlated well to the expected masses and elemental composition (m/z 212.156, $C_{16}H_{20}$; m/z 197.1325, $C_{15}H_{17}$; m/z 169.1012, $C_{13}H_{13}$; m/z 155.0855, $C_{12}H_{11}$) within mass error below ± 4.9 ppm, for the isomers. On the other hand, the use of a capillary column provided a partial chromatographic separation of isomers from Rt of 13.8 to 14.8, which is also of help as identification criteria. The identification of five DNIP isomers by GC-Orbitrap-MS was based on measurements of ions with sub ppm mass deviations (Table 2). Accurate mass data available for the series of fragment ions observed in EI spectra helped in the tentative identification with a mass accuracy equal or below 1 ppm for at least three fragment ions (m/z 197.1325, $C_{15}H_{17}$; m/z 169.1012, $C_{13}H_{13}$, and m/z 155.0855, $C_{12}H_{11}$). Table 2 shows the presence of 5 peaks from Rt 11.2 to 11.8. As can be seen in Fig. 4 there is a partial separation between the first two isomers and the two latest isomers; but separation between both couple of peaks is not sufficient for accurate results. Certainly it is necessary to contrast with standards to provide identification. If other studies are considered where the separation of the isomeric system of DINP has been derived (Bouvier et al., 2009) through both experimental and computational methods, the isomeric distribution obtained with a two-dimensional separation, using a GCxGC system, was in order of elution 1,3-, 1,7-, 2,6-, 2,7-, 1,6-. Fig. 4 shows the distribution of the isomeric system of DINP and the mass spectrum obtained by GC- Orbitrap-MS.

In up to 28% of the samples, other PAHs, such as 1-isopropyl-4,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,5,6,8a-hexahydronaphthalene, 2-isopropyl-10-methylphenanthrene, fluoranthene and pyrene were identified within mass errors below ± 1 ppm for at least three fragment ions. PAHs were detected both in areas with rural and urban influence. In 4% of the samples, fluoranthene and pyrene were identified by GC-TOF-MS with 4 characteristic ions including the molecular ion (m/z 202.0778, 200.0621, 174.0464, 101.0386) within up to 0.52 ppm of their respective calculated exact mass. Such ions correlate well to the following elemental compositions ($C_{16}H_{10}$, $C_{16}H_8$, $C_{14}H_6$ and C_8H_5) and assigned to a structure consisting of four fused benzene rings. It has been described that most of the product ions resulting from a non-resonant excitation MS activation are also observed in a resonant excitation in experiments carried out with an ion trap analyzer, giving to

a process of sequential hydrogen loss from the molecular ion. That phenomena could be related with a non selective of the ionic species generated (Pylecor et al., 1997). This is reflected in the fact that the molecular ion loses two hydrogen atoms, being more favored in fluoranthene than in pyrene. Thus a higher abundance of the $[M-2]^+$ ion in the spectrum of fluoranthene with respect to the spectrum of pyrene, is a differentiating criterion (Pylecor et al., 1997); what did not happen in this study. A different R_t in the chromatography (R_t of 16.9 and 16.2, respectively), was the criteria that helped distinguish them.

3.2. Determination of residues of veterinary treatments

Residues of veterinary treatments used for the control of varroa disease in honeybees were also detected. It is recognized as one of the most urgent problems which succumbs the beekeeping industry, if the mite population is not controlled. The fight against the mite has directly increased expenditures because of the costs associated with applying control products. On the other hand, misuse or not used in accordance with the label may alter the beehive environment and result in a damage for the normal development of the colony. Some of these treatments such as fluvalinate-tau or coumaphos are stable and accumulate in beeswax comb as result of repeated applications of the chemicals. Recycling of beeswax into comb foundation does not destroy such residues what can result in an increased level of residues in the beehive environment. In fact, a number of studies have found residues of coumaphos and fluvalinate in beehive matrices such as wax or pollen (Boi et al., 2016; Calatayud-Vernich et al., 2018; Herrera López et al., 2016; Wallner, 1999). This may lead to a chronic exposure of adult and immature bees. The bees may come into contact with residues of veterinary treatments through the strips which provide a longlasting protection against the parasite. And such residues may enter the bee body via the cuticle (dermal absorption), via oral or through the breathing system. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, the treatments most commonly used during years in both conventional and ecological management are detected even in the body of the bee. By GC-TOF-MS analysis, the tentative identification of coumaphos was based on the mass accuracies obtained for the molecular and fragment ions. The chemical formulas ($C_{14}H_{16}ClO_5PS$, $C_{12}H_{12}ClO_5PS$ and $C_{11}H_9ClO_5PS$) calculated from the accurate m/z of ions were used to assign the structure of coumaphos, with a high degree of confidence, which was generally within a 2.5 ppm absolute deviation along with a similarity among spectra and reference library with a match score of 84 (Table 1). Fluvalinate-tau is another synthetic acaricide detected in the body of adult bees. The

mass errors obtained for the molecular ion (3.3 ppm) and for up to 4 fragment ions (below 1 ppm) hence the concordance with the elemental compositions of $C_{26}ClF_3H_{22}N_2O_3$, $C_{11}ClF_3H_{12}N$, $C_8ClF_3H_6N$, $C_{10}F_3H_9N$ and $C_{13}H_9O$, and put on show this compound as Fluvalinate-tau using GC-Orbitrap-MS (Table 2). These varroa-treatments are well-known, and they have previously been reported as prevalent contaminants in honeybee hives (Herrera López et al., 2016; Mullin et al., 2010). Amitraz and its derivatives are LC amenable compounds and other pesticide residues of agricultural use with this feature are out of the scope of the GC analysis.

Beside residues of veterinary treatments authorized in organic beekeeping such as thymol, other natural compounds were detected. Among them borneol, cadinol and farnesol; the accurate mass data obtained added reliability to the tentative identification as shown in Tables 1 and 2. In the case of thymol, the measured masses of the molecular ion and the associated fragment ions are consistent with the elemental compositions $C_{10}H_{14}O$, $C_9H_{11}O$, C_9H_9 , and C_9H_7 and fits to the molecule of thymol. Borneol is a monoterpenoidal (with 10 carbon atoms) constituent of some essential oils of numerous plants; which has a broad spectrum of biological activity, widely used in drug industries, typically in folk medicine and, because of its acaricidal activity, it is also used against certain mites (e.g. species of the family Pyroglyphidae) (Bendifallah et al., 2018; Saad et al., 2006). There are two types of borneol: synthetic borneol is racemate, including four stereoisomers (+)-borneol and (-)-isoborneol, while the natural borneol only contains (+)-borneol. As shown in Table 1, the mass spectra of isoborneol and borneol have common ions and presumably, a common fragmentation pathway. The molecular ion at m/z 154 is detectable accompanied by a serie of fragment ions at m/z 136 and 139 corresponding to $[M + H - H_2O]^+$ ($C_{10}H_{16}$) and $[M + H - CH_3]^+$ ($C_9H_{15}O$), respectively. The ion 136 may yield the ion 93 by a RDA (retro Diels-Alder) rearrangement as a common fragmentation process and a successive loss of a methyl group, or the ion 95, presumably by the loss of a neutral fragment of C_3H_5 . The fragment ion at m/z 121 is probably generated from the ion 139 by the loss of a methyl group. These two isomers of borneol, isoborneol and borneol were partially separated and tentatively ascribed to the R_t of 5.2 and 5.3, respectively. Aside, the ability to perform accurate mass measurements in mass spectrometry, a precise identification of certain isomers is critical, what often occur in the terpene group. For instance, several aromatic and medicinal plants produce sesquiterpene alcohols (with 15 carbon atoms) including cadinols with an elemental composition of $C_{15}H_{26}O$. Cadinols are also stereoisomers and structurally do not exhibit a distinctiveness in the mass spectra patterns for carrying out an unambiguous identification. Table 1 shows the same serie of fragment

ions for the two isomers automatically identified by GC-TOF-MS. Up to six fragment ions are compatible with the elemental compositions $C_{15}H_{24}$, $C_{14}H_{21}$, $C_{12}H_{17}$, C_9H_{13} , C_8H_9 and C_7H_{11} associated with the structure of cadinol, with mass errors below ± 5.2 ppm. Thus, again identification relied on the retention times, tentatively attributed to β -cadinol and α -cadinol at the R_t of 13.2 and 13.4, respectively. Farnesol acetate is an acyclic sesquiterpene, present in many essential oils such as citronella or lemon grass. This compound was identified with a score of 95, when compared the spectral features against the corresponding entry in the library. The spectrum showed a pattern of characteristic ions at m/z 204, 189 and 136 equivalent to the loss of acetic acid plus a loss of neutral methyl group or alkene units (C_nH_{2n}) from the molecular ion at m/z 264 ($C_{17}H_{28}O_2$). The experimentally observed mass accuracies enabled a tentative assignment of probable elemental compositions related with such pattern ($C_{15}H_{24}$ and $C_{14}H_{21}$) with mass errors below 0.4 ppm (Table 2). In this case, although this sesquiterpene exists as four isomers, only one peak at the R_t 11.6 was detected. On the other hand, further characterization about isomerism is not feasible. The potential use of essential oils containing mixtures of terpenoid constituents as acaricides seems to be related with the molecular targets which are tyramine and/or octopamine receptors. Those control and modulate vital functions in the metabolism or behavior; thus the native function of these receptors in the mite may be disturbed and cause deleterious effects in the parasites. Nowadays, plant essential oils and organic acids are being applied as alternative to synthetic treatments to fight against *Varroa destructor*, what would explain the detection of such residues in honeybees.

4. Conclusions

The analytical methods described here, based on GC-TOF-MS and GC-Orbitrap-MS, have shown to be useful approaches for an adaptable and effective screening of non-targeted environmental contaminants. Deconvolution and comparison of the experimental spectrum data to library, offer an initial identification in an automated way, what significantly simplify the data processing. Afterward, the measurement of accurate mass provides a high level of confidence for the determination of elemental composition, elucidation of the chemical structure and tentative identification of non-targeted compounds. This step needs a careful study of mass spectra. This exploratory study has allowed the tentative identification of some GC amenable contaminants belonging to different chemical groups, among them, phthalates and PAHs, synthetic musks along with residues of veterinary treatments in honeybees. Previous related

scientific studies have put the center of attention in the monitoring of residues from veterinary treatments commonly applied in apiculture. The findings of this study evidence the presence of environmental contaminants in the body of honeybees. These results indicate that honeybees intercept contaminants such as HHCB, a ubiquitous contaminant, from water. PAHs and phthalates occur in the environment and reach the honeybees as well. There was no a clear difference about the influence of rural or urban areas. Further studies would help to evaluate routes of exposure, to understand the potential impact on honeybee and the risk assessment due environmental contaminants.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.009>.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge funding support from the National Plan for Scientific and Technical Research and Innovation 2013–2016; National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology – INIA, Ref. Project RTA2013-00042-C10-02, RTA2013-00042-C10-01. The authors also wish to acknowledge the collaboration of beekeepers.

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Fig. 1. Illustration of the sequential workflow for the screening of non-targeted contaminants using GC-TOF-MS. Tentative identification of Galaxolide. a) TIC of an extract of honeybee and deconvolution result with a representative overlapping of XIC grouped at Rt 17.36 min. Simultaneous display of unit mass EI spectral library

and sample spectra with a matching score 85.3. b) XIC of m/z 258.1972 \pm 20 ppm (corresponding to the assigned molecular formula $C_{18}H_{26}O$) and simultaneous display of the experimental isotope abundances matching well with the theoretical abundances (outlined in boxes).

Fig. 2. Illustration of tentative identification of Galaxolide by GC-Orbitrap-MS using Trace Finder. Spectral deconvolution of the TIC, library search index and the high resolution filtering (HRF) score are used for compound identification. The list of matched compounds (upper) is sorted based on a combined search index and HRF score.

Fig. 3. Elucidation of structurally related phthalates detected by GC-TOF-MS. Comparison of the experimental accurate mass spectra data to unit mass EI spectral library. Tentative identification of diethyl phthalate (DEP) and bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP).

XIC of DNP (212.156 ± 5 ppm)

Fig. 4. XIC and EI-MS spectra of diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP) 1,3, 1,7, 2,6, 2,7 and 1,6 isomers (m/z 212.156 \pm 5 ppm) analyzed by GC-Orbitrap-MS.

Table 1. Characteristics features for tentative identification of non-targeted environmental contaminants and residues of veterinary treatments in honeybee by GC-TOF-MS.

Classification	Compounds	Library score	Retention time (min)	Formula	M ^a	Mass error (ppm)	Score (mass and isotopic profile)		
Veterinary treatments – bee-hive (Insecticides/acaricides/fungicides)	Coumaphos	84	32.05	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ClO ₅ PS	362.0139	-2.5	95		
				F1	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ClO ₅ PS	333.9826	0.32	96	
				F2	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClO ₅ PS	318.9591	-2.29	73	
	Thymol	92	6.78	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O	150.1039	-0.83	85		
				F1	C ₉ H ₁₁ O	135.0804	-4.74	93	
				F2	C ₉ H ₉	117.0699	1.03	86	
	F3	88	5.37	C ₉ H ₇	115.0542	-0.39	70		
				endo-Borneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154.1352	0.66	62	
				F1	C ₉ H ₁₅ O	139.1117	7.5	81	
	F2	88	5.29	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136.1247	-4.07	85		
				F3	C ₉ H ₁₃	121.1012	7.19	62	
				F4	C ₇ H ₁₁	95.0855	-1.3	88	
	F5	88	5.29	C ₇ H ₉	93.0699	3.83	72		
				Isoborneol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154.1352	-4.99	99	
				F1	C ₉ H ₁₅ O	139.1117	-0.87	88	
	F2	92	13.49	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136.1247	-4.07	85		
				F3	C ₉ H ₁₃	121.1012	-0.53	94	
				F4	C ₈ H ₉ O	121.0648	1.04	99	
	F5	92	13.49	C ₆ H ₇ O	95.0491	0.83	99		
				F6	C ₇ H ₉	93.0699	-3.8	80	
				.alpha.-Cadinol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	222.1978	NI ^b		
	F1	90	13.21	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.1873	1.5	99		
				F2	C ₁₄ H ₂₁	189.1638	2.64	84	
				F3	C ₁₂ H ₁₇	161.1328	-0.08	83	
	F4	90	13.21	C ₉ H ₁₃	121.1012	0.04	82		
				F5	C ₈ H ₉	105.0699	5.29	45	
				F6	C ₇ H ₁₁	95.0855	4.54	77	
	F1	90	13.21	.tau.-Cadinol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	222.1978	NI ^b		
				F2	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.1873	0.14	99	
				F3	C ₁₄ H ₂₁	189.1638	0.4	92	
	F4	90	13.21	C ₁₂ H ₁₇	161.1328	-2.55	77		
				F5	C ₉ H ₁₃	121.1012	2.83	81	
				F6	C ₈ H ₉	105.0699	1.91	76	
	F1	85	17.37	C ₇ H ₁₁	95.0855	1.86	88		
				Musk fragrance	Galaxolide	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O	258.1972	-0.93	94
					F1	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O	243.1743	-0.63	96
	F2	C ₁₆ H ₂₁	213.1638		0.02	91			
	F3	83	13.86	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O	187.1117	2.12	76		
				F4	C ₁₃ H ₁₅	171.1169	-1.37	75	
				PAHs	1,3-Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	-2.8	82
	F1	C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325		-2.3	84			
	F2	C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012		4.9	78			
	F3	83	13.96	C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	-0.9	80		
				1,7-Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	-2.9	85	
				F1	C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	-3.7	82	
	F2	80	14.7	C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	1.2	84		
				F3	C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	-0.6	83	
				2,6-Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	-2.5	97	
F1	77	14.87	C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	-3.9	84			
			F2	C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	3.9	83		
			F3	C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	-1.1	87		
F1	78	12.21	1,6-Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	-0.8	85		
			F2	C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	-4.4	85		
			F3	C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	4.6	99		
F1	90	29.3	Phthalates	C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	-2.0	80		
			Diethyl phthalate (DEP)	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	222.0887	NI ^b			
			F1	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃	177.0546	0.6	99		
F2	78	12.21	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃	176.0468	0.2	100			
			F3	C ₈ H ₅ O ₃	149.0233	0.7	88		
			F4	C ₇ H ₅ O	105.0335	3.5	99		
F1	90	29.3	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390.2765	NI ^b			
			F2	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₄	279.1591	-2.5	78		
			F3	C ₈ H ₇ O ₄	167.0339	0.1	80		
				C ₈ H ₅ O ₃	149.0233	-4.8	95		

F1–F5: Fragment ions.

^a Calculated exact mass.

^b Molecular ion not present in the spectral Library or present with a very low abundance.

Table 2. Characteristics features for tentative identification of non-targeted environmental contaminants and residues of veterinary treatments in honeybee by GC-Orbitrap-MS.

Classification		Compounds	Score	HRF score	SI	Retention time (min)	Formula	M ^{+a}	Mass error (ppm)
Veterinary treatments-bee-hive (Insecticides/acaricides/fungicides)	ACARICIDES	Farnesol, acetate	95.8	99.91	791	11.67	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ O ₂	264.2084	NL ^b
		F1					C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.1872	0.39
		F2					C ₁₄ H ₂₁	189.1638	0.18
		F3					C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136.1247	1.3
		Fluvalinate	94.8	98.07	776	28.63	C ₂₆ ClF ₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	502.1266	3.39
		F1					C ₁₁ ClF ₃ H ₁₂ N	250.0605	0.29
		F2					C ₈ ClF ₃ H ₆ N	208.0135	1.03
		F3					C ₁₀ F ₃ H ₉ N	200.0682	0.53
		F4					C ₁₃ H ₉ O	181.0648	0.27
		Environmental contaminants	Musk fragrance	Galaxolide	96.2	98.7	833	13.10	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O
F1							C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O	243.1743	0.98
F2							C ₁₆ H ₂₁	213.1638	0.33
F3							C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O	187.1117	0.07
F4							C ₁₃ H ₁₅	171.1169	0.15
PAHs	1-Isopropyl-4,7-dimethyl-1,2,3,5,6,8a-hexahydronaphthalene		95	99.1	766	10.00	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.1873	0.49
	F1						C ₁₄ H ₂₁	189.1637	0.18
	F2						C ₁₂ H ₁₇	161.1324	0.19
	F3						C ₁₀ H ₁₄	134.1090	0.17
	F4						C ₉ H ₁₁	119.0855	0.76
	F5						C ₈ H ₉	105.0698	0.66
	2-Isopropyl-10-methylphenanthrene		96.3	99.6	821	18.20	C ₁₈ H ₁₈	234.1401	-0.85
	F1						C ₁₇ H ₁₅	219.1168	0.18
	F2						C ₁₆ H ₁₂	204.0933	0.01
	F3						C ₁₅ H ₁₁	191.0855	0.16
	Fluoranthene		93.5	93.36	809	16.97	C ₁₆ H ₁₀	202.0778	0.49
	F1						C ₁₆ H ₈	200.0621	0.18
	F2						C ₁₄ H ₆	174.0464	0.5
	F3						C ₈ H ₅	101.0386	0.13
	Pyrene		94.6	95.9	901	16.22	C ₁₆ H ₁₀	202.0778	0.00
	F1						C ₁₆ H ₈	200.0621	0.18
	F2						C ₁₄ H ₆	174.0464	0.5
	F3						C ₈ H ₅	101.0386	0.52
	1,3 -Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)		93.5	92.02	836	11.25	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	0.61
	F1						C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	0.30
	F2						C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	0.03
	F3						C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	0.1
	1,7-Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)		96.3	99.30	829	11.33	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	-1.89
	F1						C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	0.08
	F2						C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	0.24
F3					C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	0.19		
2,6-Diisopropylnaphthalene (DINP)	97.1	98.9	873	11.70	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	0.52		

	F1					C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	0.23
	F2					C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	0.15
	F3					C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	0.39
	2,7-Diisopropyl-naphthalene (DINP)	92.2	92.9	744	11.77	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	0.21
	F1					C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	0.30
	F2					C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	0.30
	F3					C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	0.39
	1,6-Diisopropyl-naphthalene (DINP)	94.2	96.9	769	11.83	C ₁₆ H ₂₀	212.156	0.18
	F1					C ₁₅ H ₁₇	197.1325	0.30
	F2					C ₁₃ H ₁₃	169.1012	0.14
	F3					C ₁₂ H ₁₁	155.0855	0.49
Phthalates	Diethyl phthalate (DEP)	96	99.21	814	10.50	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	222.0887	NL ^b
	F1					C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃	177.0546	0.72
	F2					C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃	176.0468	0.88
	F3					C ₈ H ₅ O ₃	149.0233	0.27
	F4					C ₇ H ₅ O	105.0335	0.81
	Phthalic acid, cyclobutyl isobutyl ester	90.4	84.7	823	14.38	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₄	276.1256	NL ^b
	F1					C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄	223.0969	0.33
	F2					C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₃	205.0859	0.01
	F3					C ₈ H ₅ O ₃	149.02332	0.07
	1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, butyl cyclohexyl ester	97.1	99.27	870	13.18	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₄	304.1669	NL ^b
	F1					C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄	223.0964	0.12
	F2					C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₃	205.0852	0.21
	F3					C ₈ H ₇ O ₄	167.0338	0.21
	F4					C ₈ H ₅ O ₃	149.0233	0.13

F1–F5: Fragment ions.

a Calculated exact mass.

b Molecular ion not present in the spectral Library or present with a very low abundance.

Supplementary Information

Exploration of environmental contaminants in honeybees using GC-TOF-MS and GC-Orbitrap-MS.

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Table S1. Location of sampled apiaries in different regions of Spain

Region of Spain	Number of samplings
Andalucía	10
Aragón	7
Asturias	2
Castilla -La Mancha	8
Castilla y León	12
Cataluña	7
Comunidad de Madrid	1
Comunidad Valenciana	6
Extremadura	7
Galicia	7
La Rioja	1
Murcia	5
Navarra	2